

Personal Attributes Associated with the Productivity of School Head Sofjolo District II

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published online: 05 November 2021	<p>This thesis entitled Personal Attributes Associated with the Productivity of the School Heads of Jolo District II was conducted with the following objectives: 1) To find out the level of personal attributes of the school administrators of Jolo District II in terms of intellectual balance, emotional balance, administrative leadership and ability to communicate, 2) To determine the level of productivity of the school administrators of Jolo District II based on their achievements in the following job areas such as articles published, financial assistance secured, extension services rendered, and innovations implemented in school, and 3) To identify if there is relationship between productivity and the personal attributes of administrators of Jolo District II.</p> <p>This study used causal descriptive because it aimed to find out if there is a relationship between personal attributes and productivity of the school administrators of Jolo District II.</p> <p>The respondents of the study were teachers of Jolo District II.</p> <p>The questionnaires were standardized hence no pre-test and post-test were needed to test the validity of the instruments.</p> <p>The findings were school administrators of Jolo District II had high level of personal attributes in intellectual balance, emotional balance, administrative leadership and the ability to communicate.</p> <p>However, they were very low in productivity that were included financial assistance and the extension services rendered, and the productivity was not significantly related to the overall personal attributes of the school administrators of Jolo District II.</p> <p>After thorough analysis and interpretation, the writer arrived at the following conclusions:1. There is a very high level of personal attributes among school administrators in Jolo District II.2. The level of the school administrators based on their achievements in the following job areas which is very poor is accepted.3. That there is no significant relationship of productivity and the personal attributes of the school administrators in Jolo District II is accepted.</p>
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INTRODUCTION

Many educators profoundly believe that our educational system is pressured by factors outside and within the school itself. This can be attributed to the untimely, unfit intervention of the disqualified political leaders; deceptive business engagement and trafficking; robust influx of globalization; skyrocketing of prices of prime commodities; unstable peace and order, social unrest to mention some. This may add to already deeply rooted post of incompetent administrator, uncommitted teachers, and poor foundation of students' academic learning.

The task of the school administrators is difficult and requires the highest degree of responsibility. The nature of his job ranges from the simplest to the most complicated one (Leveriza, 1986). The school administrator has the responsibility for determining the direction the organization takes and holds the responsibility to move it towards its goals. By virtue of administrator's action, people in the organization are motivated to contribute their best efforts and ability to the overall attainment of organizational goals (Garcia, 1989, cited by Eltagonde, 2001).

Philip Harris (1989) in his book “High Performance Leadership: Strategies for Maximum Productivity” states that leaders are more excellent executives or managers. They make things happen to achieve organizational goals and influenced planned change and organizational renewal. Thus, the principal should not be a mere personal representation of the school but he must be a leader that can contribute much to the improvements of the school systems in addition to his routinely function such as realizing school’s vision and mission.

Smilor and Kuhh (1986) quoted Jim Treybig states, “the key to productivity in any business including school system, and in fact in 90 percent of the jobs, comes from its emphasis on people. We develop concepts; we involve people in what we do... The bottom line for any business is that the major change facing the enterprise is the shifting roles of managers and individuals. Managers or principals must integrate several functions – caring about people, working on strategy, generating creativity an innovation, raising productivity, improving quality, and strengthening the organization” (Harris, 1989:5).

With this, principal or school head should have integrated skills and strategies coupled with knowledge on how to handle his employees, establish linkages, initiate relationships, provide necessary means of employees and the school purposely for the quality learning or then quality education.

Quality education is hard to achieve especially in the backward area of the province of Sulu or in the culturally disadvantaged school systems around the town of Jolo manned by myriad complexities of administrators’ personalities, but it is always a challenge to all educators or school heads. They have to plan and work as a team in order to achieved the desired objectives. Catacutan(1992) asserted that through cooperative process and group action and under atmosphere of permissiveness and cordially, much can be done to improve quality education in school system.

Angara (1986) emphasized that the first consideration for the effective management of the school’s human resources is the quality of its administratorship. He stated further that the school administrator must be a creative as his faculty, as purposeful; and determined as the personnel he leads and as democratic and participative as the community he represents.

The school administrator must have the professional preparation and personal qualities to meet the demands of his varied roles in school (Nitura, 1984; cited by Eltagonde, 2001). Thus, this study purports to underscore personal attributes of school administrator such as intellectual balance, emotional balance, administrative leadership and ability to communicate as it is related to productivity of that includes published articles, books, references, initiate assistance and others.

RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

The efficient and effective performance of all administrative functions will lead to high organizational productivity. Schermerhorn (1986) explicates his views on the subject thus:Productivity is a summary measure of the quantity and quality of work performance with resource utilization considered. From the administrator’s perspective, productivity reflects performance measure. It identifies the success or failure in producing goods or services in quantity or quality, and with a good use of resources.

The issue of resource utilization highlights another facet – the human resource utilization in the performance process. Productivity is ideally achieved through high performance activities and delegates authority to his subordinates for an appreciation of the enterprise traditions, history, and its objectives and policies. Under staffing, the executive selects, trains and recommends candidates for higher responsible positions. Under controlling, he compels events and situations to conform to plans for their accomplishments.

Gregorio’s (1978) categorization of the administrative functions includes the following: planning the school programs and activities, directing school work, and formulating and executing educational policies, providing the necessary leadership, evaluating the teaching staff and personnel, keeping records and reporting results.

He states that it is the responsibility of the school administrator to encourage the teaching staff, administrative and supervisory officials, parents, and students to cooperate in planning the school program. The administrator should also work out definite policies, rules, and regulations and embody them into a program.

Being the professional leader of the school, the administrator shall coordinate all the activities of the school in order to attain the desired goals. A school survey is conducted to evaluate whether the school is properly implementing its policies, and to evaluate the performance of the teaching staff and other personnel. The school and with sense of personal satisfaction by the people doing the work, both performance and satisfaction should result when managers work with individuals and groups to achieve productivity. Administrators are increasingly expected to facilitate productivity while maintaining the quality of working life for its members.

A major past of very administrator’s job therefore is to establish and maintain the conditions for productivity. High productivity, in turn, requires more appropriate technology and skilled workers. It requires their creative and successful combination into a well – functioning total performance system.

PERSONAL ATTRIBUTES OF ADMINISTRATORS

The success of a school administrator does not depend only on education an experience, Andres (1987) opines. His personal characteristics such as dynamic leadership ability, creativity, willingness to try new approaches, and ability to relate with superiors and subordinates contribute a great deal to his success as a school manager. The other qualities he must possess mental health, ability to communicate with others, patience and high degree of objectivity toward other individuals.

In a similar view, Catacutan (1992) quoted McCormick and Tiffin as including in the list a factors that might be associated with the relative performance of individuals, such as factors as aptitudes, personality characteristics, interest and needs, sex, age, education, experience, and other personal variables.

Steers (1984) supports this claim by saying that the person’s abilities and traits largely determine his capacity to perform. These capabilities grow in importance as individuals move up the managerial hierarchy into increasingly responsible positions. Abilities and traits are believed to be enduring overtime, but some changes are possible as a result of outside intervention.

For managerial success, intellectual ability seems to be particularly important (Gannon, 1978). It can be measured in a general way by means of standard tests or the individual’s academic preparation. Both scholastic knowledge and the knowledge and skills that come from experience are widely known to be important to an individual’s success.

A school administrator must prove that he is competent, that he has leadership potential like intellectual and emotional maturity. He must possess an analytical mind, common sense, self-confidence, self-respect and an optimistic outlook (Sadagnet, 1983). The leader gains the respect of the teacher when he leads because he towers above them all in competence and ability.

The importance of personal factors in the development of a desirable pattern of leadership behavior is that intelligence, abilities, skills and interest developed are vital human resources for educational administrator’s competence. The author advocates the development personal attributes as foundations for advancing the status of educational leadership (Catacutan, 1992).

Leadership is a skill that is desired and respected but is seemingly difficult to attain for many people. School administrators must possess this skill so that individual and organizational goals in the school system are achieved. He is concerned with the shaping of the quality of education towards the improvement of the quality of life of the people (Catacutan, 1992).

But an individual can function as leader only through his relationship and effective communication with other persons as Aquino (1985) stresses. The administrator’s ability to communicate is an important but often neglected aspect of administrative behavior.

All administrators must possess adequate skills in communication if they are to effectively perform their managerial functions. When good communication exists from the top of the organization downward as well as upward and through the different levels in the organization, high performance can be expected (Abasolo,1991).

Stoner, et al. (1987) explained that the process of communication makes it possible for managers to carry out their task responsibilities. Information must be communicated to managers so that they will have a basis for planning; the plans must be communicated to others in order to be carried out. Organizing requires the managers to communicate with subordinates so that group goals can be achieved. Written or verbal communications are essential part of controlling. In short, managers carry out the management functions only by interacting with and communicating with others. The communication process is thus the foundation upon which management functions depend. Changes in its external environment and adapts its objectives, activities and outputs to the requirements of that environment.

PERFORMANCE OF ADMINISTRATIVE FUNCTIONS AND PRODUCTIVITY

The administrator’s job is to help the school achieve a high level of performance through the utilization of its human and material resources. Effective management solicits increasingly awareness of and concern for better performance.

In performance analysis, it is essential that a wide range of factors be considered. These factors include individual characteristics of an intellectual, emotional, motivational and physical nature; influence from groups such as work unit and the family; organizational factors; aspects of social context; and effective deriving from the work environment including economic forces; geography, and the nature of the work setting (Miner and Miner, 1985).

Educational administrators are expected to perform efficiently and effectively the important aspects of the administrative work, which includes planning, directing, coordinating, leading, evaluating, and reporting. The successful performance of the people who lead the organization depends on so many factors, among them personal and environmental. Studies relating performance of these functions to the aforementioned factors are herein presented.

Jakaria (1992) tried to appraise the administrator’s performance of administrative functions and found out that

they did not often practice the planning, directing, and organizing functions because of the highly centralized and regulated educational system. The coordinating, evaluating, leading, and public relation functions were seldom practiced due to the “bahalana” attitude. All factors such as economic and social forces, educational laws and policies, financial and budgetary constraints, values and attitudes, political influence, group pressures and educational training and qualifications of administrators influenced their performance of administrative functions.

The level of performance of administrative functions of elementary school principals was also studied by Nagasan in 1992. Based on the findings of her study, she conducted that majority of the principals had served as administrator for one (1) to five (5) years, had the necessary qualifications for their positions, and had attended regional level in service trainings. The administrator’s general appraisal of their performance of all the functions was “Very Satisfactory”.

Reyes, as cited by Catacutan (1992) also investigated the performance of principals and found out that their personal and professional qualifications made them competent in their application of democratic administrative principles in the performance of their functions. Their teachers acknowledged their competence by rating them “Very Satisfactory” during the survey.

The correlates of managerial competence of academic managers of state colleges and universities in Region XI was the focus of Quinoy’s (1988) research. The self-rating of the top, middle, and low level academic managers revealed that they were highly competent school managers who rated themselves to be proficient in their management styles and experts in planning, informing/communicating, time management, and delegating. He also found out that the length of administrative experience and number of in-service trainings on management were not correlated with managerial functions. On the other hand, educational attainment and managerial competence were positively correlated.

PRINCIPAL’S BEHAVIOR

This competent of school climate pertains to the leader’s style of interacting with the teachers. The way the principal behaves, as has been noted, influences the ways in which the teachers interact with each other and thus has considerable impact on the general atmosphere of the school. Four aspects of the principal’s behavior that were identified as important by Halpin and Croft (see Halpin, 1966: 152-154). These are aloofness, production emphasis, thrust, and consideration.

Aloofness refers to psychological and physical distance from teachers that the principal typically maintains. Degree of formality is another way of interpreting this facet

of the principal’s behavior. Conducting faculty meetings as if they were business meetings, adhering to a tight agenda, establishing firm rules for teachers, and withholding the results of classroom visits are examples of aloofness on the principal’s part. As Halpin (1966: 151) noted aloof behavior is universalistic rather than particularistic. Principals vary greatly in this dimension of their behavior, ranging from highly to not all aloof.

Production emphasis refers to the degree of active supervision the principal typically exercises over staff. Degree of assertiveness in the supervisory role is another definition of production emphasis, which includes such actions as scheduling teachers work hard. Strong production emphasis, in the framework, is associated with downward communication and insensitivity to teachers’ reactions (Halpin, 1966: 151). Principals differ in this aspect of their behavior, from being emphatic in supervision to paying scant attention to teachers’ productivity.

Thrust pertains to the active, energetic role – modeling aspect of the principal’s behavior. Personal drive and vigor are alternative interpretations of thrust. Arriving early and staying late, setting a good example by working hard, and being active and interested in new educational developments are all examples of high thrust. A leader characterized by high thrust does not expect teachers to give more of themselves than he or she does (Halpin, 1966: 151) but sets a high standard for everyone. Principals may range from exhibiting high thrust to having virtually no thrust at all.

Consideration is a concern for staff members as individual beings; it is synonymous with kindness and humanitarianism. This dimension of leader behavior is exemplified by such actions as doing personal favors for teachers, helping them both in their work and in their personal lives, and standing up for the teachers’ best interests. Considerate behavior is particularistic rather than universalistic. Principals vary greatly in this characteristic, ranging from highly considerate to not at all considerate.

These four dimensions of principal’s behavior pattern – aloofness, production emphasis, thrust, and consideration – are conceptually independent of each other. Knowing the principal’s typical behavior with respect to one dimension does not help one to determine his or her behavior with reference to the other dimensions. One would have to assess all four aspects individually to derive a profile of the principal’s behavior pattern.

LEADERSHIP IN ORGANIZATION

Among the most widely studied of organizational and small-group phenomena, leadership has been conceptualized in numerous ways. A behavioral approach to leadership research was initiated by Andrew Halpin and others at the Ohio University as the leader behavior description

framework. Two major dimensions of behavior were found, though much empirical research, to be exhibited by people occupying leadership positions in organizations; the person-oriented dimensions, including tolerance of uncertainty, tolerance of freedom, consideration, demand reconciliation, integration, and predictive accuracy; and the system-orientation dimension, including production emphasis, initiating structure, representation, role assumption, persuasiveness, and superior orientation. Both aspects of behavior are viewed as essential for effective leadership (Halpin, 1966; Stogdill, 1974).

A situational view of leadership – one emphasizing the impact of circumstances on the leader’s effectiveness – is Fred Fiedler’s contingency model. In this framework the leader’s personality or leadership style – task oriented or relationship oriented – is of prime importance, as is the degree of favorableness of the group – task situation. Three aspects of the group – task situation – leadership-member relations, task structure, and leader position power – are combined to determine the degree of situation favorableness, and the performance of the group is viewed as dependent of the matching of leadership style and situation favorableness. More specifically, task oriented leadership matched every favorable or unfavorable situations is said to yield optimal group performance situations yields optimal group performance (Fiedler, 1967).

These two approaches to leadership research concern different aspects of organizational interaction, but they can be seen as complementary perspectives. The leader with a given personality (task oriented or relationship oriented) interacts with a group in a particular social setting (situation favorableness) and, as a result, exhibits a distinctive pattern of behavior (person oriented and system oriented). This behavior pattern in turn stimulates the group toward greater productivity or hampers the group’s productive efforts. One cannot assume that a task-oriented leader will behave in a system-oriented manner of that a relationship-oriented leader will exhibit person-oriented behavior. Instead, one can assume that a given situation will affect a task-oriented leader’s behavior in one way and a relationship-oriented leader’s behavior in another. Stated differently, the leader’s behavior as it influences the group’s efforts can be viewed as emerging from the combined effects of the leader’s personality and situation.

RESEARCH ON EDUCATIONAL ADMINISTRATION

Only one published study of schools was located in which all three major constructs were operationalized. Although the curvilinear relationships posted by the theory were not found in this study, elementary school principals’ conceptual levels were found to be related to the complexity of their interpersonal environments and to the frequency of their person-oriented leadership behaviors (Silver, 1975). That is, the more conceptually complex principals had more

functions performed in their schools, more professionally oriented faculty members and more frequent interactions with faculty; they also exhibited greater tolerance of uncertainty and freedom, greater consideration for teachers, and greater predictive accuracy.

There is contradictory evidence on the behavior patterns of leaders having different conceptual levels. Although the studies tend to confirm that more complex leaders are more frequently person oriented in behavior (Silver, 1975; Burrus, 1979; Streufert, and Castore, 1968), some research reveals no differences between groups of leaders in system-oriented behavior (Silver, 1975; Burrus, 1979), whereas, other research reveals less complex leaders to be the more system oriented in behavior (Streufert and Castore, 1968). In an indirectly related study, Croft (1965) found “open-minded principals to be no better than “closed-minded” at predicting other’s perceptions of their behaviors. In the one remaining study of administrators’ behaviors, conceptually simple superintendents regarded fewer, more concrete, and more authoritarian negotiation roles as suitable, compared with their more complex counterparts (Moellenberg and Williams, 1969). An ancillary finding in the studies of educational administrators was that the large majority of them have simple or moderately simple conceptual systems.

BEHAVIORAL COMPLEXITY

Behavioral complexity varies to the degree that behaviors require or show evidence of differentiation, discrimination, and integration on the part of the behaving individual. Classes of behaviors such as decision making, communicating, and problem solving can represent relatively few or many differentiations and integrations in the conceptual system of the person who is behaving. Variations in the complexity of behavior patterns can be illustrated with reference to three classes of behaviors, as follows.

Decision making can vary in complexity depending on the range of information used, the amount of conflicting information incorporated in the decision, and the certainty or authoritativeness with which the decision is rendered. Relatively simplistic decision making entails little search for information, quick closure or arrival at a decision, exclusion of conflicting or discrepant information, and high certainty that the decision was correct. Complex decision making entails a broad search for information; absence of complete closure (that is, no final, irrevocable decision is reached). Inclusion of conflicting or discrepant information; and uncertainty about the correctness of the decision (see Suedfeld and Streufert, 1966).

Communication can vary in complexity depending on the extent to which messages sent are categorical, authoritarian, similar or predictable, and generalizable as

rules. Relatively simple communication patterns are characterized by categorical, authoritarian, predictable, and rule-bound statements. Complex communication patterns, at the other extreme, include statements that are conditional, speculative, varied or unpredictable, and sensitive to the particular audience.

Problem solving is a class of behaviors that can vary in complexity depending on the range of alternative solutions sought, the degree of rigidity in combining bits of information and how programmed or predetermined the solution are. Simplistic problem solving is characterized by consideration of few alternative solutions. Rigidity (conformity with habitual patterns) in combining pieces of information, and programmed (predictable) solutions. Complex problem solving, on the other hand, entails considering a broad range of alternative solutions, combining pieces of information flexibly (in many different ways), and inventing novel or unexpected solutions.

PRODUCTION

Theoretically, higher production is associated with greater centralization (1), greater stratification (V), and greater formalization (1), but less complexity (6). This suggests that in schools with relatively centralized decision making numerous hierarchical levels, considerable job codification, and standardization of procedures, but with little differentiation of functions and relatively little professional training, student outcomes can be expected to be greater than in schools structured differently.

With reasonable limits, some of these relationships make sense. Although advisory participation of faculty and students in the decisions that affects them is desirable, the administrator, who has the broadest view of the school and its environment, might be in the best position to make final decisions. School leaders can increase centralization without reducing participation by having faculty and student committees legitimately serves in an advisory capacity. Increased stratification can also have beneficial effects, as has been demonstrated in schools that have adopted a differentiated staffing pattern. In these schools, the most expert, so that the effective techniques of these so-called master teachers are more widely disseminated throughout the school.

In addition, clearly defining the various jobs in the school and establishing explicit procedures for dealing with routine matters, as in more formalized schools, can reduce confusion within a school and also reduce the time spent on duplication of activities and on trivial matters. In this way administrators can increase the time available for teachers to devote to the creative enterprise of educating children.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Any undertaking in the school system should have at least a concern of the school administrator. In turn, the

administrator may influence this undertaking as it primarily occurs in the course of instruction, publish materials, construction of school buildings, financial aids and others. The interplay, therefore, of personal attributes of the administrator and the increased productivity of the school as it is determined by administrator, himself, will occur in the school setting. Usually, educators consider the performance of the administrator as a determinant of quality education. Meaning, administrator must possess quality attributes, which will result to quality output.

This study sought answer to the following questions:

1. What is the level of personal attributes of the school administrators of Jolo District II in terms of:
 - a. intellectual balance,
 - b. emotional balance,
 - c. administrative leadership, and
 - d. ability to communicate?
2. What is the level of productivity of the school administrators based on their achievements in the following job areas such as
 - a. articles published,
 - b. financial assistance secured,
 - c. extension services rendered, and
 - d. innovations implemented in school?
3. Is there significant relationship between personal attributes and the productivity of school administrators in Jolo District II?

METHODOLOGY

This study used causal descriptive because it aimed to find out if there was a relationship between personal attributes and the productivity of the school administrators of Jolo District II. It may only include productivity and personal attributes as enumerated in the statement of the problem might be the cause of productivity.

The respondents of the study were the selected teachers based from scientific approach. They were selected without prejudice to their age, gender, number of preparations and other variables inherent in the respondents.

The statistical tools used were mean and correlation test to assert the hypotheses of the study.

Mean was used for the computation of the level of personal attributes of the school administrators of Jolo District II in terms of intellectual balance, emotional balance, administrative leadership and ability to communicate.

It was also used for the computation of the level of the productivity of the school administrators based on their achievements in the following job areas such as articles published, financial assistance secured, extension services rendered, and innovations implemented in school.

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Mean was computed by using this formula.

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum X}{n}$$

Where:

- \bar{X} = mean
- $\sum X$ = summation
- n = number

Correlation was used for the computation of the significant relationship between personal attributes and the productivity of school administrators in Jolo District II.

The questionnaires were standardized hence no pre-test and post-test were needed to test the validity of the instruments.

The whole populations such as teachers and principals were used to avoid biases on the selection.

The study was conducted among the schools of Jolo District II such as Riverside Elementary School, Port

Area Elementary School, Dan-Dan Ututalum Elementary School, Lambayong Elementary School, Laud Lambayong Elementary School, and Bus-Bus Elementary school.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Personal Attributes of the School Administrators of Selected Elementary Schools in Jolo District II in terms of Intellectual Balance, Emotional Balance, Administrative Leadership and Ability to Communicate

Intellectual Balance

Table 4.1 showed the findings about the level of personal attributes of the school administrators of Jolo District II in terms of intellectual balance. Based on the computed mean of each of the seven functions, it can be pointed out that the school administrators had high level of personal attributes in said intellectual balance. That is, the following practices of functions were done in many occasions on instances: 1. possesses general knowledge. 2. Possesses specific knowledge. 3. analyzes problems intelligently and objectively. 4. Intellectually critical of existing standards, systems and policies. 5. Displays a functional knowledge of the tasks and responsibilities that must be met. 6. Knows how to give instruction to subordinates. 7. Improves himself professionally by attending in-service training programs or weekend classes.

Table 4.1.Level of Personal Attributes of the School Administrators of Jolo District II in terms of Intellectual Balance.

Personal Attributes	Level	
	Mean	Descriptive Interpretations
1. Possesses general knowledge.	4.06	High
2. Possesses specific knowledge in his own field.	4.06	High
3. Analyzes problems intelligently and objectively.	3.92	High
4. Intellectually critical of existing standards, systems and policies.	4.18	High
5. Displays a functional knowledge of the tasks and responsibilities that must be met.	4.16	High
6. Knows how to give instruction to subordinates.	4.36	High
7. Improves himself professionally by attending in-service training programs or weekend classes.	4.28	High

- Legend:** 1.00-1.45=Very Low (VL)
 1.50-2.45=Low (L)
 2.50-3.45=Moderately High (MH)
 3.50-4.45=High (H)
 4.50-5.00=Very High (VH)

Naval and Aquino (1978) further stressed the need of intellectual balance as a component of qualification of a school administrator and supervisor. The principal, they averred, should possess a specific and general knowledge. Specific knowledge is referring to a field of specialization such as mathematics, English, or human relation skill; while

general knowledge refers to related theories in the school administration and supervision.

Abasolo (1998) in his “Personal Management” said that the executive should have a skill in solving problems so as to anticipate its impact to the organization and, principals of Jolo District II were not in exemption to this.

More so, to grow professionally, one should attend training and development (Sison, 1991). In the elementary level, trainings just very recently centered on educational training related to BEAM programs, ASCEND – EQUALLS, and other foreign programs. Besides, policy conference was usually sponsored by the DepEd, Division of Sulu. Hence, these present principals have the room for more improvements in their field of executive jurisdiction.

Emotional Balance

As portrayed in table 4.2, the means or averages of all the seven practices under emotional balance fall under the point interval of 3.5 to 4.45. This meant that the level of

personal attributes of the school administrators in terms of such emotional balance was high. In other words, the school administrators highly performed the following functions or practices: 1. Is emotionally poised and calm. 2. Has adequate self-confidence. 3. Is concerned with own problems. 4. Welcomes differences in viewpoints. 5. Has a high degree of tolerance for tension resulting from increasing volume of work, organization change, environmental conflict, etc. 6. Maintains calmness and proper composure in the face of critical situations. 7. Understands his weaknesses and strong points and can discuss them with objectivity.

Table 4.2.Level of Personal Attributes of the School Administrators of Jolo District II in terms of Emotional Balance.

Personal Attributes	Level	
	Mean	Descriptive Interpretations
1. Is emotionally poised and calm.	4.22	High
2. Has adequate self-confidence.	4.30	High
3. Is concerned with own problems.	4.26	High
4. Welcomes differences in viewpoints.	4.04	High
5. Has a high degree of tolerance for tension resulting from increasing volume of work, organization change, environmental conflict, etc.	4.14	High
6. Maintains calmness and proper composure in the face of critical situations.	4.18	High
7. Understands his weakness and strong points and can discuss them with objectivity.	4.28	High

Legend: 1.00-1.45=Very Low (VL)
 1.50-2.45=Low (L)
 2.50-3.45=Moderately High (MH)
 3.50-4.45=High (H)
 4.50-5.00=Very High (VH)

Leveriza (1990) explained that a leader should be calm and has high degree of tolerance. He should not decide when he is in state of anger and hunger to prevent from misjudging. In short, he must be emotionally stable.

In relation, the principals of Jolo District II demonstrated high degree of emotional balance. As such, they can treat the problem with objectivity and, they can reconcile individual differences: differences of opinions, views, motives and beliefs.

Kahne (2006) stressed the need to reconcile societal divides or organizational divides so as to abridge the gaps among people within the organization. Talking, telling, listening, facilitating or other strategies could be employed to facilitate differences. Similarly, if these differences are abridged, then, stable organization shall primarily visible or notable.

And not only that, what is desirable is the principal acknowledgement of their weaknesses because it is really a

venue to personal and professional development. And, this should be stressed by individual not only the principal but the teacher as well.

ADMINISTRATIVE LEADERSHIP

In terms of administrative leadership, the level of personal attributes of school administrators of Jolo District II were high (Table 4.3). This is, the seven practices of the administrators were highly done in many instances in the District II of Jolo. These include the following: 1. Welds staff into a unit clearly recognized goals. 2. Uses democratic procedures whenever possible. 3. Inspires his subordinates to do independent and creative work. 4. Encourages peers and subordinates to contribute and participate in problem-solving and decision-making. 5. Delegates authority to staff or next-line supervision to develop leadership potential. 6. Persuades, inspires and encourages his subordinates to attain better performance. 7. Stimulates subordinates to start and initiate new concepts, ideas and methods.

Table 4.3.Level of Personal Attributes of the School Administrators of Jolo District II in terms of Administrative Leadership

Personal Attributes	Level	
	Mean	Descriptive Interpretations
Administrative Leadership		
1. Welds staff into a unit clearly recognized goals.	4.14	High
2. Uses democratic procedures whenever possible.	4.22	High
3. Inspires his subordinates to do independent and creative work.	4.22	High
4. Encourages peers and subordinates to contribute and participate in problem-solving and decision-making.	4.24	High
5. Delegates authority to staff or next-line supervision to develop leadership potential.	4.24	High
6. Persuades, inspires and encourages his subordinates to attain better performance.	4.14	High
7. Stimulates subordinates to start and initiate new concepts, ideas and methods.	4.12	High

Legend: 1.00-1.45=Very Low (VL)
 1.50-2.45=Low (L)
 2.50-3.45=Moderately High (MH)
 3.50-4.45=High (H)
 4.50-5.00=Very High (VH)

Nowadays administrators are existing much efforts to gain the confidence of his subordinates. In a school setting, it would be very difficult to make the teachers legal to the administrators considering that the teachers themselves have varied experiences, set of beliefs, bits of ideas and preferences. However, in Jolo District II, the principals demonstrated high performance in administrative leadership. It did mean that these principals had approaches and strategies especially in the means of management principles such as motivation and organizational relationship.

Leveriza (1990) pointed out that there must be a corresponding authority commensurate to delegate responsibility to sustain and even improve institution. And not only that, it must be coupled with inspiration and motivation that persuades teachers to exhaust their efforts and express their commitment towards schools vision and objectives.

Besides, innovation on organizational dynamic meeting the challenges around school should be initiated. Changes therefore within the components of the school system should be facilitated so as to avoid risk and disorganized components or system breakdown (Stoner and

Wankel, 1987). On the same view, school administrators in Jolo District II were not far off from these practicalities on theoretical translation into blatant actions.

Successful could it be that Jolo District II had the space for improvement and visible achievements in educational endeavor.

ABILITY TO COMMUNICATE

As depicted in Table 4.4, the means of all the five practices under the attribute of ability to communicate fall under point of interval of 3.5 to 4.45, which indicates high level of personal attribute of those school administrators in terms of said ability. These five practices include the following: 1. Knows how to give directions and briefing to staff and subordinates. 2. Explains and discusses very well with the staff and teachers every school activity. 3. Gives organized and adequate information requested by subordinates and keeps them posted on relevant changes. 4. Gives instruction to teachers that are well discussed and clearly understood by them. 5. He “puts in writing” so that subordinates are not at an informational disadvantages. In other words, those five practices were highly done by the school administrators in Jolo District II.

Table 4.4.Level of Personal Attributes of the School Administrators of Jolo District II in terms of Ability to Communicate

Personal Attributes	Level	
	Mean	Descriptive Interpretations
Ability to Communicate		
1. Knows how to give directions and briefing to staff and subordinates.	4.26	High
2. Explains and discusses very well with the staff and teachers every school activity.	4.34	High
3. Gives organized and adequate information requested by subordinates and keeps them posted on relevant changes.	4.20	High

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4. Gives instruction to teachers that are well discussed and clearly understood by them.	4.44	High
5. He “puts in writing” so that subordinates are not at an informational disadvantages.	4.32	High

Legend: 1.00-1.45=Very Low (VL)
 1.50-2.45=Low (L)
 2.50-3.45=Moderately High (MH)
 3.50-4.45=High (H)
 4.50-5.00=Very High (VH)

To effectively coordinate all stakeholders of the educational system including the actors changing the responsibilities in the delivery of educational service is through clear communication process especially the principal. Leveriza (1990) aptly called “communication” as an organization itself because it primarily links every component in the school so as to achieve relevant and dynamic educational setting.

Koontz and Weihrich (1997) labeled that the essence of management is coordination and this can be achieved through communication. Also, leading expert, Chester Barnard, said that the major function of the executive is through communication because it provides meaning and relationship to every department, section, or member in the organization. Laudable as it was that the school principals of Jolo District II performed significant indicators. It did mean that they demonstrated very high performance.

Yes, the set of questions (see questionnaires) were more on top – bottom questions, thus, the principals need to be tested on the bottom – up questions so as to see if they could still perform similar with what this study purposed.

Level of Productivity of the Selected School Administrators based on their Achievements in Articles Published, Financial Assistance Secured, Extension Service Rendered, and Innovations Implemented in Schools

Table 5 shows the mean of the points as well as the descriptive interpretation for each of the four job areas of productivity of the school administrators for schools in Jolo District II.

In terms of articles published-books, scholarly research, monographs and educational technical articles, the level of productivity is very low. In the case of books, only one out of six administrators in the district was able to have done publication, and she had published there different units with her role as co-author in the year 2000 to 2002. For the published scholarly research, monographs and educational technical articles, no one of them has done publication. As to the institutional manual and audio-visual materials, only one out of six was able to acquire certain instructional materials with three different titles or types. As such, the means of the points for each sub aspects of articles fall under the bracket of 0 to 1, indicating very low productivity as stated earlier.

Financial Assistance Secured

As to financial assistance secured two out of six administrators had done initiating the requirement of the needs of school, especially on the aspect of library facilities, buildings, infrastructure, athletic equipment and others, with the total points of 13 as depicted in Table 5. The mean of the points a school heads is 2.16 indicating that the level of productivity in terms of financial assistance secured is also very low.

Extension Services and Innovations Tried out

The school administrators in Jolo District II had very low level of productivity in terms of extension services and innovations tried out. The mean of the points for each of these two aspects are 0.833 and 1.33 respectively, indicating low level (Table 5). The total points as rated is only 13 coming only from two out of six school heads. The remaining four were not be able to initiate extension services nor try out innovations in school.

Table 5. Level of Productivity of the School Administrators based on their Achievement in Articles Published, Financial Assistance Secured, Extension Service Rendered, and Innovations Implemented in Schools.

Job Areas of Productivity	Level		
	Sum of Points	Mean	Descriptive Interpretations
A. Articles			
1. Books (Textbooks, References)	4	.66	VL
2. Published Scholarly Research, Monographs, Educational Technical Articles	0	0	VL

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3. Institutional Manual and Audio-Visual Materials	3	.50	VL
B. Financial Assistance Services	13	2.16	VL
C. Extension Services Rendered	5	.83	VL
D. Innovations Tried out	8	1.33	VL

Legend: For articles For financial assistance For extension and innovations
 0-1 (VL) 1-2.9 (VL) 0-1 (VL)
 2 (L) 3-4.9 (L) 2 (L)
 3 (H) 5-6.9 (H) 3 (H)
 4 or more (VH) 7 or more (VH) 4 or more (VH)

Relationships between Personal Attributes and the Productivity of School Administrators in Jolo District II
 Table 6 showed the correlation matrix showing the relationship between the personal attributes and productivity achievements of the administrators. In the case of articles published, productivity in terms of books, has no significant relationship with each of the four different personal attributes – intellectual balance, emotional balance, administrative leadership and ability to communicate. That is, such achievement in books published might not be associated with nor affected by the personal attributes. There

are no data available for the case of published articles as depicted in the table. Institutional manual was found inversely related significantly to the intellectual balance and administrative leadership.

Finally, the overall productivity was not significantly related to the overall personal attributes of the school administrators of elementary schools in Jolo District II in terms of intellectual balance, emotional balance, administrative leadership, and ability to communicate.

Table 6. Correlation Matrix showing the Relationship between the Personal Attributes and Productivity of School

	Personal Attributes				
	Intellectual	Emotional	Administrative Leadership	Ability to Communicate	Overall
Attributes Productivity					
1. Books, (Textbooks, References	.304	.549	.304	-.039	.304
2. Published Scholarly Research, Monographs, Educational Technical Articles	---	---	---	---	---
3. Institutional Manual and Audio-Visual Materials	-.845	-.566	-.845	.101	-.845
4. Financial Assistance Services	.383	-.224	-.299	-.059	-.294
5. Extension Services Rendered	.169	-.157	-.541	.135	-.541
6. Innovations Tried Out	0	-.315	-.621	.207	-.621
<i>Overall Productivity</i>	.319	-.103	-.377	-.058	-.377

Correlation is significant at the .05 level (2 – tailed)

Productivity is always an expected output of any endeavor in addition to routine functions. Productivity can be in terms of improved quality services, enhanced skills, or quality ideal graduates.

However in most cases, the productivity has been a problem in all organizations because of various factors.

In school setting such as Jolo District II, the principals demonstrated very low productivity. Out of the six elementary principals, only two (2) had productivity in terms of learning materials and had secured sports equipment despite of their very high intellectual balance, emotional balance, administrative leadership and skills in communication.

Majority of them reasoned out that there were busy implementing routine matters inherent in the position. Others lamented that the Revised Basic Elementary Curriculum (RBEC) requires arduous task in the implementation. As such, they had not initiated for any materials to be published.

In management principles, it is not enough for the principal to be intellectually and emotionally prepared if only to excel the academic outputs, but he should be creative, resourceful and innovative in the sense he could provide what the school needs in terms of material facilities and others. Also resourceful he should find ways to established linkage with other donor agencies amidst the economic constraints haunting the government and the school. Besides innovative of the principal is, so that he could revised the learning materials that best fit to the levels of the pupils.

Hence, the principal should be wise enough in sourcing out funds. Securing programs and projects from the donor agencies, and revising the reading materials of the pupils and the teacher alike.

Leveriza (1990) classified the types of decision based on the function demonstrated by the officials. These decisions are called non-programmed and programmed decisions. And the principals were confined to exercising programmed decisions which theoretically speaking could be delegated to subordinates.

With these subordinates should be formed into group and be given short course training in the implementation of RBEC so that the principal had enough time to increase and improve their productivity.

Unless the RBEC implementation would not be delegated to group of subordinates, the principals could not experience improved productivity despite their being very high performance in intellectual balance, emotional balance, administrative leadership and communication process.

RECOMMENDATION

1. The Department of Education should organize a team composed of faculty members to lead in the implementation of RBEC.
2. The school principals of Jolo District II should delegate the lead of implementation to the assigned head of related subjects so as to lessen the burden in the implementation of RBEC.
3. The school principals of Jolo District II should establish the linkages with the donor agencies to avail with the books, facilities and materials needed by the pupils.
4. Follow-up studies on the factors affecting productivity should be conducted.
5. DepEd officials should encourage principals to write articles and be published them in the magazines, newspapers and others.

CONCLUSION

After a thorough analysis and interpretation, the writer arrived at the following conclusions:

1. There is a very high level of personal attributes among school administrators in Jolo District II.
2. The level of the selected school administrators based on his achievements in the following job areas is very poor is accepted.
3. That there is no significant relationship of productivity and the personal attributes of the selected school administrators in Jolo District II is accepted.

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